

AquaLink: The Next-Gen Hydration Solution

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ABSTRACT: In the contemporary IT landscape, non-living entities seamlessly engage with each other, intelligently adapting to changing conditions. The Internet of Things (IoT) emerges as a transformative technology, encapsulating the essence of computing. This article provides a concise exploration of IoT-enabled water bottles. Water, fundamental to human existence, undergoes quality variations influenced by numerous factors. The intelligent water bottle, equipped with touch and photoplethysmographic sensors, adeptly gauges liquid levels, tracks activity through inertial sensors, and captures physiological characteristics via touch and photoplethysmographic sensors. Through continuous real-time monitoring facilitated by input sensors, the system analyzes data and, when necessary, employs actuators to enact appropriate responses. This approach holds considerable value for health-conscious individuals in today's society and exhibits potential applications in the healthcare industry, where heightened caution is imperative across various domains.

Keywords: Multitask Cascaded Convolutional Neural Network (MTCNN), Convolutional neural network (CNN), Facenet, Age Invariant Features, Face Embedding, Facial Landmarks.

I. INTRODUCTION

The term "Internet of Things" may be small, yet its capabilities transcend what was once considered miraculous just a few decades ago. In our rapidly evolving world, nearly any object, ranging from televisions and refrigerators to watches, shoes, and clothing, has smart counterparts. These objects, originally designed for singular purposes, now serve a multitude of functions, with IoT serving as the catalyst for imbuing inanimate objects with intelligence.

The core concept of the Internet of Things revolves around extracting data from input sensors. The process involves processing and aggregating information from raw data, evaluating the data, and making decisions based on a set of algorithms or protocol rules. Various types of actuators are then employed to execute actions based on these decisions.

The Smart Interactive Water Bottle serves as a valuable tool in assisting users to monitor their daily water consumption effectively. With features such as tracking the daily amount of water consumed and calculating the average intake, users gain insights into their hydration habits. The bottle also provides information about the last water intake time, promoting awareness of regular hydration throughout the day. One of its notable functionalities is the ability to send reminders to the user, encouraging timely water consumption to maintain optimal hydration levels. Additionally, the smart bottle alerts users when it is time to refill, ensuring that they never run out of water. This comprehensive set of features aims to enhance user well-being by promoting consistent and mindful hydration practices. The incorporation of a pH sensor and turbidity sensor in the smart water bottle represents a significant advancement, empowering users to assess water quality conveniently while on-the-go. This innovative feature not only enhances the user experience but also promotes health-conscious hydration practices. By providing real-time information about the pH level and turbidity of the water being consumed, the smart water bottle enables users to make informed decisions about the quality of their hydration. This capability is particularly valuable in situations where water quality may vary, ensuring that users can prioritize their health by choosing water that meets their desired standards. Overall, the inclusion of these sensors contributes to a more comprehensive and personalized approach to hydration, aligning with the growing trend of health-conscious consumers seeking smart solutions for their daily routines.

The integration of solar charging technology in the smart water bottle represents a noteworthy stride towards sustainability and eco-friendliness. This innovative feature harnesses sunlight to power the device, significantly reducing reliance on conventional charging methods. By utilizing solar energy, the smart water bottle not only promotes environmental responsibility but also enhances user convenience. Users can enjoy the benefits of continuous device functionality without the frequent need for conventional charging, contributing to a greener and more energy-efficient lifestyle. This eco-friendly approach aligns with the growing global emphasis on sustainable technologies and reinforces the smart water bottle as a conscientious choice for individuals seeking both technological innovation and environmental conservation in their daily lives.

The inclusion of a GPS locator in the smart water bottle introduces a valuable and user-centric feature, providing individuals with the ability to pinpoint the bottle's location effortlessly. This innovative technology ensures that users can locate their smart water bottle with precision, even in situations where it has been misplaced or lost. By leveraging GPS capabilities, users gain peace of mind knowing that they can easily track and retrieve their water bottle whenever needed. This feature not only enhances convenience but also minimizes the potential stress and frustration associated with misplacing personal

items. Overall, the GPS locator in the smart water bottle is a practical addition, contributing to a seamless and stress-free user experience.

The integration of a mobile app for the Smart Water Bottle represents a significant leap forward in user engagement and health-conscious hydration. This feature empowers users to seamlessly track their hydration levels, receive personalized reminders, and access real-time data, fostering healthier drinking habits directly from their smartphones. Users can input key information such as age, weight, activity level, and health goals, allowing the app to calculate personalized daily hydration goals tailored to individual needs. The smart bottle's LED indicators provide a quick at-a-glance view of water levels, while the LCD display offers in-depth insights and detailed data for a more comprehensive understanding of hydration patterns. Additionally, the NodeMCU serves as a communication hub, enabling the smart water bottle to send timely alert messages to predefined Telegram contacts. This not only facilitates remote monitoring but also ensures an immediate response to critical situations, enhancing the overall effectiveness and safety of the smart water bottle system.

Figure 1.1: Prototype of a Smart Water Bottle.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Market Adherence: Dana De Meo and Michael Morena have worked to break one of the major problem in healthcare center, that's cases not taking drugs capsules at specified time and missing it due to colorful reasons which causes detention of results in treatment. Around 60 of the people face this problem and have trouble in getting well. This bottle can be connected to the pall and transfers data about the volume content outside and also the cap open/ close timing. Lights and chimes are actuated at the right/ correct/ prescribed time of input. These signals can be fluently visible and audible. It can also be customized according to the assiduity and client as per the operation.

1. Hydration Reminding Smart Bottle: IoT Experimentation:

Dr. P.B. Pankajavalli, Mr. R. Saikumar, and Mr. R. Maheswaran have introduced a novel concept involving a smart water bottle designed to prompt individuals to consume water at regular intervals, preventing dehydration. The water float sensor within the bottle is responsible for detecting the water level, signaling whether it is low or high. The RS232 chip plays a crucial role in determining the communication type and instructing the GSM modem, which facilitates voice and data services, to establish communication with electronic devices and mobile phones. Subsequently, individuals receive SMS notifications on their mobile screens, reminding them to stay hydrated by drinking water. It's noteworthy that the power consumption for this innovative model is maintained at a low 5V.

2. IoT BASED SMART WATER BOTTLE:

J Laxmi Lahari proposed the idea of water bottle which can help us in keeping track of the quantum of water we drink. It also reminds to refill the water bottle and assists the consumer to ameliorate his water drinking habits. An ultrasonic detector is installed inside the cap of the bottle which is leakproof in nature. It'll help in determining the water position inside the bottle for which the labors will be shown in Adafruit IO feeds. Its data changes with change in the position of water. The buzzer rings whenever the water position is zero inside the bottle and stops once the bottle is refilled. It also rings to remind the consumer to drink water if he hasn't drank for further than 2 hours. This promotes a healthy life.

3. A Self-monitoring Water Bottle for Tracking Liquid Intake:

Bo Dong, Ryan Gallant, and Subir Biswas have worked on a water bottle which target the input of water regularly as it's the introductory need of mortal body and it's demanded for its normal functioning. They principally made a band and attachment which can be attached to any normal water bottle and make it a smart Bottle by tracking the input of fluid of the stoner. It's a Bluetooth based device which will shoot all the details about drinking habit of the stoner to their separate smartphones when connected and remind them to drink if the input is low at regular interval of time. It principally works on the discovery of volume of fluid/ water inside the bottle. The stylish part about it's that we don't need the whole bottle we just need a band and can attach it to any regular water bottle and make it a smart bone.

4. GROW: A Water Bottle that Use its Surface as Display to Motivate Water Intake:

Gul Kaner, Deniz Erdogan, Huseyin Ugur Genc created a water bottle named 'grow'. It's a abstract to encourage druggies to drink water. As we know water is a introductory demand for mortal body. still, individualities ignore drinking water due to their busy schedule. So they developed a bottle which would help people to meet their quotidian water conditions. This bottle is bedded with liquid position sensor and uses bottle face as an ambient display to track and cover quotidian water consumption of an existent. A bottle also contains a thermo- chromic print over the face of bottle, so that by toast different corridor of print, bottle gives positive, aesthetic and non- protrusive feedback.

5. Accuracy of daily fluid intake measure using a "smart" water bottle:

Borofsky MS et al. have worked on water bottle which helps to measure the input of fluids by the person using it, especially used for high input for order gravestone cases. It uses touch seeing and measures the position of water outside. It can each be watched viewed over the smart phones with all the data day wise using an operation. Survey was also done on people for 2weeks to check bottles pros and cons. It came out to be effective within 3 range. It can be a great and cost effective measure to reduce drop like order monuments without any drug just by helping the person to input right quantum of fluid per day.

6. Healthcare Services and a Water Bottle for Seniors Citizens:

Nam Eui Lee, Tae Hwa Lee, Seo Dong Heui, Sung yeon kim discovered a smart water bottle and give healthcare services to old peoples. In old people the central jitters tend to decelerate down due to which the body lacks water. They organize lots of checks, perceptivity & also give a structure of correct water input habits. They came with a fact that 75 of respondants are not feeling thirsty and 47 input water designedly for health purpose indeed they weren't thirsty. utmost of the respondents are on drug, which also affects the water input effectively. It isn't easy to form new habits. So they all created a bottlegrounded on iot technology which is equipped with weight detector and other functions also, to track and cover diurnal waterconsumption of an existent a bottle also contains a thermo chromic print over the face of bottle

III. THE PROPOSED METHOD

IV. RESULTS

Using LCD display presents all hydration-related values, ensuring easy access to information at a glance. Users can conveniently view water levels, hydration statistics, and reminders directly on the bottle. The mobile app mirrors the information displayed on the bottle's LCD screen Users have access to real- time hydration data, personalized reminders, and insights via their smartphones for on-the-go monitoring and tracking.

Figure 2. Results

V. CONCLUSION

By seamlessly integrating technology with everyday hydration, it promotes healthier lifestyles and environmental sustainability. From tracking water levels to assessing water quality, this innovative solution sets a new standard for smart hydration devices. The Smart Interactive Water Bottle is more than just a hydration tool—it's a companion for better living.

VI. REFERENCES

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